

The effect of perceptual versus conceptual fluency on brand evaluation for luxury brands in a data rich online environment

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Introduction

According to the processing fluency model, advertising exposures enhance the ease with which consumers recognize and process a brand. In turn, this increased processing fluency leads to consumers having more favorable attitudes toward the brand. In other words, consumers base their product evaluation and brand choice decisions not only on information they have about the brand but also on how easy it is for them to process the information.

Moreover, processing fluency may be perceptual or conceptual in nature (Tulving & Schacter, 1990). Perceptual fluency reflects the ease with which consumers can identify a target stimulus on subsequent encounters and involves the processing of physical features such as modality (e.g. visual vs audio vs pictorial) and shape (Jacoby & Dallas, 1981). Conceptual fluency on the other hand, reflects the ease with which the target comes to consumers' minds and pertains to the processing of meanings (e.g. Hamann, 1990; Monroe & Lee, 1999). Although the effect of perceptual fluency on affective judgment is well documented (e.g. (Reber, Winkielman, & Schwarz, 1998)), fewer studies have examined the effects of conceptual fluency on affective judgment (with the exception of (Lee, 2004)). However, brands, particularly luxury brands, rely heavily on stories and narratives to convey brand meaning. The effect of brand narratives on consumer brand evaluation is obtained via conceptual fluency, and is particularly prevalent for online communication.

Digital and online advertising has grown by 15% from 2015 to 2016 in the UK and accounts for 40% of all advertising revenue (Mintel, 2016). In comparison, TV advertising accounts for only 25%. Social media is of particular interest, as 41% of all social media users notice advertisements. Facebook and Twitter are amongst the most popular social media platforms (Department for Culture Media & Sport, 2016). How to achieve processing fluency in a data rich environment where consumers find themselves in a '*perpetual state of partial attention*' (Batra & Keller, 2016) is a timely and important question for brand communication researchers and practitioners. Therefore, the objective of our research is to examine the differential role that perceptual and conceptual fluency play on affective judgment and brand evaluation for luxury brands in the data rich online environment.

The processing fluency model

Fluency refers to a consumer's subjective metacognitive experience of ease or difficulty in retrieving information from memory or processing external stimuli, such as marketing communication (Schwarz, 2004). Mere exposure research shows that recent exposures to a target render the target more readily accessible in memory; in turn, this increased accessibility enhances the ease with which consumers identify and recognize the target, which is referred to as "processing fluency" (Jacoby & Dallas, 1981).

According to the processing fluency model, advertising exposures enhance the ease with which consumers recognize and process a brand. In turn, this increased perceptual fluency leads to consumers having more favorable attitudes toward the brand. In an experiment by Reber, Winkielman and Schwarz (1998), higher perceptual fluency was achieved by presenting a matching rather than nonmatching prime before showing a target picture. Participants judged targets as prettier if preceded by a matching rather than nonmatching prime.

Because the stimuli used in previous research were often novel or simple stimuli (e.g. drawing, abstract paintings) that discourage participants engaging in more meaningful processing, the enhanced

processing fluency that resulted from the prior exposures is more indicative of how easily participants can perceptually identify and process the stimuli (i.e. perceptual fluency) than of how readily stimulus comes to mind and its meaning is activated (i.e. conceptual fluency) (Lee, 2004). Whittlesea (1993) manipulated conceptual fluency by presenting words in a neutral or predictive semantic context (“The evening gown was missing a . . . bead” vs. “The bored student opened her mouth to . . . yawn”). The words that appeared in the predictive context were pronounced faster indicating enhanced processing fluency, and were judged as more pleasant. However, Whittlesea’s findings leave unclear whether the predicted words were rated as more pleasant because of high processing fluency or because they were consistent with the semantic context whereas the unpredicted words were somewhat incongruous with the semantic context. Moreover, Whittlesea’s findings leave open if perceptual, as opposed to conceptual, manipulations of fluency can enhance preference.

Type of brands and construe level

According to the theory of psychological distance, brand communication using concrete language reduces the psychological distance between the brand and consumer. Thus, consumers perceive such a brand as accessible and affordable (Liberman & Trope, 1998; Trope & Liberman, 2000). Conversely, brand communication using abstract language increases psychological distance and consumers perceive products advertised in such a manner as desirable and exclusive. Thus, the former communication style is more suitable for functional brand type, whereas the latter is more suitable for luxury brand type. In other words, the level of construal differs depending on brand type, i.e. luxury vs. functional brands. Luxury brands are exclusive, hedonic, desirable, and consumed less frequently than everyday functional brands (Hirschman & Holbrook, 1982; Liberman & Trope, 1998). Conversely, functional brands are accessible, affordable, and serve a means-end purpose. Therefore, they are represented more concretely in consumers’ minds than luxury brands.

(Dis)fluency generated by (mis)matching construal level

It is found that repeatedly perceived stimuli are more easily processed resulting in perceptual fluency, which refers to a sense of familiarity based on repeated encounters with a stimulus (Schwarz, et al., 1991; Reber, Winkielman, & Schwarz, 1998). Previous studies show that processing fluency enhances message authenticity, credibility and trustworthiness (Hansen & Wänke, 2010), leads to more favourable brand attitudes (Lee, Keller, & Sternthal, 2010), and impacts the call to action positively (White, MacDonnell, & Dahl, 2011).

In the context of online communication, we define fluency as when marketing communication matches consumers’ brand perception in terms of concreteness. Concreteness is the measurable outcome the theory of psychological distance (Trope & Liberman, 2010), according to which consumers think less concretely about luxury brands than functional brands. This is because luxury brands are desirable whereas functional brands are feasible. Feasibility is construed more concretely whereas desirability is construed more abstractly (Liberman & Trope, 1998). Combining concreteness with fluency theory, we predict that a concreteness mismatch decreases fluency and has ultimately a negative impact on consumers’ brand evaluation, as shown in Figure 1 below:

How brand communication can generate fluency and positive consumer responses

Figure 1: Conceptual model

Empirical studies

This paper comprises four studies: one psycholinguistic computational study and three experiments. Study 1, the psycholinguistic computational study is to measure and compare concreteness in marketers' brand communication and consumers' brand perception.

Study 1: Computational psycholinguistic study

Methods: We measured the concreteness of 1590 Facebook posts per post and 6000 tweets per tweet from businesses to consumers and vice versa with three data sets. The first data set includes 3000 consumer tweets to 15 luxury and 15 functional brands. The second entails 3000 company tweets for the same 15 luxury and 15 functional brands. The last contains 1590 Facebook brand communication posts including consumer likes and reactions. The tweets and posts underwent a data cleaning process in which numbers, website links, emoticons, and special characters were removed. The remaining linguistic content of tweets and posts were rated according to word concreteness ratings found in a published database (Brysbaert, Warriner, & Kuperman, 2014), which has been widely used in other psycholinguistic studies (Hills & Adelman, 2015; Klebanov, Leong, Heilman, & Flor, 2014; Kuperman, 2015; Vinson, Thompson, Skinner, & Vigliocco, 2015).

Findings: The selected brands represent brand type, i.e. luxury vs functional brand, well on Twitter and reasonably on Facebook. Consumers use significantly more abstract words when tweeting luxury brands than functional brands. Therefore, when consumers communicate with luxury brands they consider them as desirable and exclusive. How desirable luxury brand are, is reflected in the amount of likes their Facebook posts receive. They receive significantly more likes on average ($M = 11295.67$) than functional brand posts ($M = 120.60$). Consumers click on average 333 times on the love reaction icon of a luxury brand post – significantly more than on a functional one ($M = 3.64$). Investigating the relationship between likes and the concreteness of advertisement language, we found a significant but non-linear relationship. Specifically, posts with an average concreteness score of 2.66 and above attract more likes. Concrete (abstract) words are more (less) vivid in memory, thus more (less) effective at triggering an instant response, such as Facebook likes. This finding confirms theoretical predictions, but illustrates the dichotomy brand managers face: exclusivity vs. being accessible for everyone.

Investigating luxury and functional brand communication on Twitter and Facebook, we could not detect the same pattern suggesting a mismatch between communication styles. Combining the consumer and company Twitter datasets, we conducted a 2 (company vs consumer) by 2 (brand type: functional vs

luxury) ANOVA. The results support our prediction about a communication style mismatch. The interaction between who is tweeting, i.e. company vs consumer, and brand type is not significant. Our computational psycholinguistic analysis of Twitter and Facebook data show that functional (luxury) brand communication construes differently from how consumers construe the same brand. Consumers construe luxury brands more abstractly than they do for functional brands. However, no significant difference is found for brand communication indicating a mismatch between how consumers perceive luxury brands and how brands communicate to them. Therefore, in study 2, a 2X2 experiment is conducted to examine whether the mismatch between the levels of construal for luxury and functional brands affect consumers' brand attitude and liking.

Study 2:

Methods: A match in communication style occurs when luxury (functional) brands communicate abstractly (concretely) with consumers. Conversely, a mismatch in communication style reflects luxury (functional) brands communicating concretely (abstractly) with consumers. We manipulated the level of construal in brand communication to examine whether different levels of construal in brand communication impact consumer evaluation of different types of brand. We ran a 2 (concrete vs abstract brand communication) by 2 (luxury vs functional brand) by 2 (brand logo presence vs absence) within subjects experiment with 37 Undergraduates from a British university. Participants ranked four real Facebook advertisements from Primark and CHANEL on a scale ranging from 1 (extremely desirable, exclusive, expensive) to 5 (not at all desirable, exclusive, expensive). Presenting participants an abstractly (concretely) worded advertisement with the CHANEL (Primark) logo represents the match condition. Showing participants an abstractly (concretely) worded advertisement with the Primark (CHANEL) logo represents the mismatch condition. To create a baseline condition participants rated the same advertisements once with and once without brand logo. In addition, we collected whether participants' native language is English or not.

Findings: A repeated Multivariate Analysis of Variance revealed significant differences between level of concreteness and luxury vs functional brand on desirability, exclusivity and expensiveness ratings. Abstractly (concretely) worded advertisements are perceived as more (less) desirable, exclusive and expensive. Whether participants' first language was English or not did not significantly influence the results. The 3-way interaction concreteness * brand type * brand logo is significant overall (multivariate) as well as for each of the three outcome variables. Showing participants a matching stimuli for luxury brands, i.e. abstractly worded advertisement with the CHANEL logo, resulted in more favourable ratings on all three outcome variables in comparison to showing a mismatching stimuli (concretely worded advertisements with the CHANEL logo) and the base line condition. Showing participants a matching vs nonmatching advertisement for functional brands gave more complex results. While a match decreases desirability and expensiveness ratings, it marginally increases exclusiveness ratings in comparison to a mismatch. Comparing the match and the baseline conditions, exclusivity and expensiveness ratings were slightly lower in the match condition than the baseline condition. A possible explanation is that fluency may impact consumer evaluations differentially depending on brand type.

In sum, Study 2 has shown that a concreteness mismatch has potentially profound implications for consumer brand evaluation. However, it has not directly tested the mechanism for such effect, namely processing fluency. Therefore, next, Study 3 will investigate how a concreteness mismatch affects processing fluency, which in turn influences consumer brand evaluation.

Study 3:

Previous studies have manipulated fluency by means of difficult to read font type, duration of stimulus presentation, (mis)matching two subsequent stimuli, (mis)matching the context of a target word in a sentence, figure-ground contrast, and number of recalled items (see for example (Reber, Winkielman, & Schwarz, 1998; Winkielman & Cacioppo, 2001; Novemsky, Dhar, Schwarz, & Simonson, 2007;

Whittlesea, 1993; Schwarz, Bless, Strack, Klumpp, Rittenauer-Schatka, & Simons, 1991; Tsai & McGill, 2011). We plan to manipulate participants' construal level to show that a mismatch in concreteness decreases fluency and ultimately communication effectiveness leading to less favourable outcomes. Therefore, this will be a 2 (concrete vs abstract processing) x 2 (concrete vs abstract advertisement language) within subject design. Participants will be primed to think about going shopping the forthcoming week-end (concrete) or in a year (abstract) (Liberian, Sagristano, & Trope, 2002). Fluency measures will be collected with a seven-point scale ranging from 1 (easy) to 7 (difficult) to process based on previous studies (Lee & Labroo, 2004; Hong & Sternthal, 2010). In addition, we will collect brand familiarity measures for both brands.

Study 4:

While processing fluency may be a likely explanation, we do not know whether perceptual fluency or conceptual fluency is driving this processing fluency effect. Perceptual fluency is generated by a match in concreteness, while conceptual fluency is triggered by the salience of the semantic brand associations in consumers' memory. Lee and Labroo (2004) found that both perceptual and conceptual fluency influence processing fluency and evaluations, but they seem to be independent of each other. In light of the results for functional brands, showing participants a concretely worded advertisement with the Primark logo decreasing desirability ratings, this warrants further investigation. Therefore, we will manipulate stimuli to activate conceptual fluency and to test how conceptual fluency will differentially influence consumers' brand evaluation compared to perceptual fluency for brands.

Summary and conclusion

Study 1 shows that consumers consider luxury (functional) brands as more (less) abstract, exclusive and desirable based on the language they use to tweet them. Inversely, luxury brands do not match their communication style in terms of concreteness. Study 2 shows that a match in communication styles results in more favourable evaluations for luxury brands, but not necessarily for functional brands. Based on fluency theory we suggest that perceptual fluency (match in concreteness) and conceptual fluency (salience of brand associations) impact consumers overall evaluation differentially and aim to investigate this in study 3 and 4.

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